

EMBEDDED SYSTEM BASED EDUCATION MODEL FOR LEARNER'S IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The whole world is undergoing a change. The learning and the way a learner acquires knowledge will also be evolving and changing in post pandemic world. The design of learning content, classroom, laboratories etc. is very important for achieving desirable learning outcomes. That is the reasons all the accreditation bodies are focusing upon outcome based education. The paper presents the new definition and designs of the learning space (i.e. classrooms, laboratories etc.), learning material and also presents how big data has impacted the implementation and incorporation of technology for improvement in learner's learning experience. The paper focuses specially on use of big data techniques for estimating the learning pattern of students. The proposed work was evaluated and results shows that the proposed model can be adopted in any educational organization for investigating the learning experience of students/learner's through implementing it in educational embedded system module.

KEYWORDS: *Big data, educational model, big educational data, analytics, quality improvement, educational embedded system.*

1. Introduction

The pandemic has brought drastic change to the education system. There are evolving lots of challenges in creating, providing, and maintaining the education standards and meet growing the demand for online education. The system is evolving and once the things and situation return to normal a big challenge is to provide quality education to the students so as to improve their performance [1-4]. The learning space and learning material play an important role in learner's performance. The good quality learning material should have seven important elements that makes the content easily understandable by any learner. The learning material should be attractive and desirable i.e. it should be in the form that is interesting and easy to understand. It should have sufficient number of illustrations, images, graphs, charts etc. to support the content. The content should be designed in a way that reader should be able to connect with it. However, a content that is attractive and beautifully designed but do not add to the existing knowledge of the learner is also not useful.

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Fig. 1. Seven elements of good learning material

It should invoke interest, should be easily accessible and should provide rich learning experience to the reader. Figure 1 shows seven elements of quality learning material. Similarly, the learning space also plays a very important role on the performance of the learner's. Figure 2 shows components of quality learning space. In figure 2 there are five elements of educators and learner experience that directly relate with the learning requirements of educator and learner. The necessary indicator for each of the element are also shown though these indicators are not exhaustive but covers most the elements.

Fig. 2. Key elements of learning space

2. Methodology

To evaluate the quality of learning material and learning space a big data based analysis model is given

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in figure no. 3. First of all data is collected from the existing educational model and visual analytics is carried out. On the basis of this analysis of learning material and learning space a model is evolved after data analysis and information visualization. This evolved model is evaluated through analytical reasoning, if results are as per the requirements than model is applicable to improve the quality of learning material and learning space, otherwise the process is iterated till the model improves and validates as per the specifications. The visual analytics and observations shown in figure 3 are used to manipulate the data obtained from the educator's and learners [5-8]. The process of visual analytics is supported by interactive visual interfaces, information visualization, analytical reasoning and visual perception.

Fig. 3. Analysis of educational model visualization and big data analysis

On the basis of this model a complete system diagram for an educational organization is developed. Figure 4 shows data driven approach for analysis of educational model. The model is for an educational institute. So the inputs are: student details, organization byelaws, faculty profile, lecture notes, assignments, notices, extracurricular and co-curricular activities and soon. The inputs are acquired in form of big data, analyzed on the basis of these, a model is predicated and the results are actionable outputs to be acted upon. The process from action plan to current / existing systems in use involves several steps which are repeated / interacted in terms of quality parameter and quality indicators to give an enhanced & improved quality of learning space and learning material.

Fig. 4. Big data driven analytics of educational model

The model if carefully interpreted, it could be found that the input to model is data fed from extreme left and output is action plan or decisional report to act upon. The main focus of the approach was to acquire maximum data, process it, analyze it and store it for future retrieval. In the presented model the analysis starts by capturing the data and then dataflow through various processing steps. In the first step high volume of input data is useful as bigger is the size of data better are the predictions of result. Though there is a tradeoff between better results and computational overheads require more storage overheads such as more storage space, complex data mining requirements, better computational system, software applications and latency. All this acquired data has to be processed and analyzed with help of expertise and skills based on educational data mining, after analyzing the acquired data with the help of reference skill set and comparing it with standard quality parameters an action plan is generated to be acted upon. Finally, the action plan can be referred or remarked for improvement by iterating from step 1.

3. Implementations

The model shown in figure 4 is converted in to physical data set and a program based on the module is pre-loaded in the memory of educational embedded system module. The figure 5 shows the block diagram of ST microelectronics STM32F7791 [9] based educational embedded system. This module can be easily adopted and deployed in any educational system to collect, analyze and control the educational environment as per the given education model in figure 4. The figure 5 shows the main processor which is the heart of complete system, it is connected to main memory which is preloaded with educational model to be implemented. Along with this several modules such as sensors, student management system, classroom management system, employee management system audio, video, graphic and disk management system to make the whole module independent and autonomous.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of educational embedded system module

Fig. 6. STMicroelectronics STM32F7791 embedded system development board [9]

Figure 6 shows the real implementation of the educational embedded system module on STMicroelectronics STM32F7791 embedded system development board. It has 34MB on chip RAM and 64 MB NAND Flash.

4. Results and Analysis

By involving the proposed model with improved learning space and learning material students are able to perform better and hence classroom results will improve. Students are not more passive acceptors but are actively involved so they develop better thing skills, analyze information from a broader perspective. The students develop a problem solving skill by formulating and discussing new ideas. Figure 7 shows the comparative learners performance before & after implementation of the educational
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embedded system module.

Fig. 7. Comparison of learners performance before and after applying educational model

5. Conclusion

The presented model was evaluated and it was found that it can be effectively adopted in any educational organization. The paper effectively demonstrated the use of big data analysis tool applied to different areas of educational data for data manipulation and analysis. The big data analysis techniques not only helped in predictive analysis but is also useful and beneficial for enhancing the quality of education provided to the student. The presented educational embedded system module was tested and it showed that it improved the learning experience of the students thereby improving their performance. In the modern era of innovation and technology the big data has an important role to play. It will have an available impact on the quality of learning space and learning material provided to the student thereby improving overall quality of educational system. In future the presented module can be extended to further analyze the physiological, psychological and social behavior of a learner.

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